

A Review Paper on Strengthening of Sub Grade Pavement by RBI Grade-81 for Flexible Pavement

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1. SOIL STABILIZATION

Soil adjustment or alteration alludes to the change of the dirt physically or synthetically by utilizing different strategies including mechanical compaction and the utilization of different calcium rich chemicals. The choice of appropriate adjustment strategy relies upon the dirt kind and its condition. Mechanical adjustment is most appropriate for coarse grained soils or totals at ideal or beneath ideal dampness substance. In any case, clayey soils are more viable under compound adjustment. On the off chance that the clayey soil is blended with the particular stabilizer sufficiently only to make it workable, better in surface and similarity notwithstanding the quality and strength, at that point it is alluded to as alteration (Indiana DOT, 2002); adjustment is limited to the dirt having AASTHO assignment A-4, A-5, A-6 and A-7 (Oklahoma DOT, 2009). Then again, adjustment alludes to the choice of the stabilizer keeping in mind the end goal to accomplish certain objective quality/firmness esteems notwithstanding alteration. Adjustment is fundamental in the event that we are managing development of sub base in asphalts and making working stage for development reason.

OBJECTIVES OF STABILIZATION:

Improvement of engineering properties of the soil mass, specifically by stabilization:

- Detrimental settlements can be reduced or prevented.
- Soil strength can be increased and slope stability improved.
- Bearing capacity of pavement sub grades can be increased.
- Hydraulic conductivity can be decreased.
- Undesirable volume changes-caused, for example, by frost action, swelling, and shrinkage of fine-grained soils may be controlled.

➤ METHODS OF SOIL STABILIZATION

Currently several methods of soil stabilization are available with their own advantages and disadvantages. The engineer in charge has to decide a method or a combination of methods by considering the soil type, the needed engineering properties to be improved, and the type structure, and economy. Stabilization methods can be broadly classified into two main groups. They are mechanical and chemical. Additionally thermal and electrical methods are also considered on occasions. Important stabilization methods and their suitability are discussed in the following paragraphs.

A. Mechanical Stabilization

Mechanical stabilization is the most inexpensive method and suitable for most varieties of soil groups. his strategy comprises of two systems for modifying the dirt properties, to be specific, the reworking the dirt particles, alteration of soil structure and the enhancing of the dirt degree. Molecule improvement is expert by mixing diverse soils, and alteration of soil structure is accomplished by densification by compaction.

B. Dewatering

Dewatering is additionally a mechanical technique that includes in the expulsion of or lessening in undesirable overabundance ground water.

C. Preloading

In preloading strategies, establishment soils are surcharged with an impermanent over-burden to expand the quality and lessening expected settlements.

D. Lime Stabilization

Lime is being used as a soil stabilizer since ancient times. The hydrated lime $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is the most commonly used lime for soil stabilization. Lime is also used in combination with other stabilizers such as fly ash and Sisall fiber. Soil plasticity, density and strength are changed by adding lime to soil. Lime builds the pliancy record of low plastic soils and abatements the versatility file of high plastic soils. All kinds of soils can be settled utilizing lime.

E. Polymer Stabilization

Regular polymeric materials, for example, gums and manufactured polymeric materials, for example, polyvinyl liquor (PVA) have been utilized as soil stabilizers. These polymers waterproof fine-grained soils and grant quality and diminishing penetrability.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. REVIEW OF PREVIOUS STUDIES ON SOIL STABILIZATION USING RBI GRADE-81

This chapter deals with the study of black cotton soil, various

methods of stabilization of black cotton soil, its need and its advantages. In addition to this the research work done by various authors to make the black cotton soil stable i.e. to with stand the stresses on the pavement structures, improvement in the CBR value after stabilization by using different stabilizing materials is also reviewed.

1. **B.M. Patil, K.A. Patil, and L.K. Kokate, 2012** conducted a study on the use of Industrial Waste like Pond ash, Fly Ash, Stone dust, Foundry Sand and Steel Slag for Soil Stabilization. In the present investigation, the different proportion of soil sample, Pond ash, and RBI Grade-81 were prepared. Pond ash was mixed in the proportion of 10% and 20% and RBI Grade-81 was furthermore blended in the proportion of 0%, 2%, 4%, and 6%. On the basis of result, they concluded that with the addition of pond ash and RBI Grade-81 the CBR value increases. when soil: pond ash: RBI 81 were blended in the proportion of 74:20:6 the CBR value increased up to 775% of untreated soil. CBR qualities expanded with expansion in the rate of RBI Grade 81. This inferred that the industrial waste materials like fly ash and pond ash can be used as the stabilizer with clayey soil.
2. **K.V. Madurwar, et. al., (2013)** conducted a study on the effect of sodium silicate and RBI Grade-81 on the black cotton soil to improve its engineering properties. The test results showed that Liquid limit decreased and plastic limit increased with the addition of admixture, thus resulting in a reduction of the plasticity index. The UCS and soaked CBR values increased with increase in RBI Grade-81, suggest its suitability as good stabilizer. But with the increasing dose of sodium silicate UCS and CBR value decreased, which indicating the limitation of sodium silicate to be used as a stabilizer. when the RBI Grade-81 was added to the soil the free swell index value was decreased but with the addition of sodium silicate it was increased.
3. **B. M. Patil, K. A. Patil, (2013)** studied the effect of RBI Grade-81 and moorum to stabilize the soil. The RBI Grade-81 and moorum were mixed with soil in different proportions and tested for OMC, MDD and soaked CBR. The soaked CBR of untreated soil was 2.56%. when the soil and RBI were mixed in the proportion of 98:02 & 96:04 the soaked CBR values were increased to 4.89% & 8.79%. when soil was mixed with moorum in the proportion of 90:10 & 80:20 the soaked CBR values were increased to 2.41% and 2.84%. The soaked CBR values for the mixture soil, moorum and RBI Grade-81 in the proportions of 88:10:02, 78:20:02, 86:10:04 & 76:20:04 were found to be 3.4%, 4.56%, 10.23% & 14.76%. The conclusion made on the basis of test results was that the CBR value of soil can be improved by using moorum and RBI Grade- 81 as a stabilizer.
4. **Haricharan T. S. at. al., (2014)** conducted a laboratory investigation of expansive soil stabilized with natural inorganic stabilizer. In the laboratory they have conducted the atterbergs limit test, compaction test, CBR test and UCS test with the addition of 0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, 2% and 2.5% RBI with black cotton soil. The CBR test was performed after 1 day, 3 days and 7 days of curing and UCS test were performed after 0 days, 7 days, 14 days and 28 days of curing period. The plasticity index of soil and OMC value were decreased and MDD increased with the increase of RBI percentage. The CBR of untreated soil was 1.34% which increased to 14% with the addition of 2.5% RBI-81 after 7 days of curing period. The UCS of untreated soil was found to be 208 kN/ which increased to 1032 kN/ at 2.5% RBI addition with 28 days of curing. With the investigation of test result, the authors concluded that RBI Grade-81 is a good stabilizer to stabilize the black cotton soil.
5. **Tejinder Singh and Navjot Riar, (2015)** investigates the effect of RBI Grade-81 to stabilize the soil with the help of Atterberg's limit test, Standard Proctor test and CBR test and analyze the cost difference between conventional method and cost of pavement constructed using 2%, 4%, 6% and 8% RBI Grade-81. The CBR value of untreated soil was 2.14% which has increased to 28.9%, 60.82%, 105.01% and 135.5% with the addition of 2%, 4%, 6%, and 8% RBI Grade-81 after 7 days of curing period and 4 days of the soaking period. After the test, they concluded that RBI Grade-81 is very effective in stabilizing the highly plastic soil. This soil can be considered as stabilized sub base. They also concluded that expense of pavement reduced with RBI Grade-81. The pavement cost found to be minimum among all other cases when it constructed with soil and 2% RBI Grade-81. The cost of the pavement by the conventional method was nearly 3 lacs which become approximately half with the addition of 2% RBI Grade-81.
6. **Lekha B.M. and A.U. Ravi Shankar, (2015)** conducted a study on the performance of RBI Grade-81 in the laboratory to stabilize the soil for pavements. The soil and stabilizer RBI-81 mixed in different proportion and tested for atterberg's limit, OMC, MDD, UCS, and CBR. The UCS of untreated soil was 380 kN/ and unsoaked UCS of soil mixed with RBI-81 in the proportion 98:02, 96:04, 94:06 were found to be 265kN/, 380 kN/ , 475 kN/ after 1 daays curing period and 830 kN/ , 1350 kN/ , 1800 kN/ after 28 days curing. The CBR values for soil and stabilizer proportion 100:00, 98:02, 96:04, 94:06 were found to be 0.3%, 4.5%, 9.3% and 12.5% after 7 days curing and 4 days soaking period. On the basis of results, they concluded that the strength of BC soil improved appreciably with the stabilizer under unsoaked condition. The CBR value of soil showed good improvement when treated with 6% stabilizer. They also determined the fatigue life (number of cycles) of treated soil at repeated loads corresponding to one third and half of UCS strength of 98:02 soil: RBI mix cured for 7 days and 28 days. Best results were obtained with 6% stabilizer after 7 days and 28 days curing period at one third corresponding UCS strength values for 2% stabilizer both at 7 days and 28 days curing period in which fatigue life increased to 4172 after 7 days curing and 8005 after 28 days curing period. The fatigue life of untreated soil was obtained 3 after 7 days curing and 5 after 28 days curing period at one third corresponding UCS strength values for 2% stabilizer.
7. **Manisha Gunturi et. al., (2016)** carried out a study on CBR and swelling behavior of expansive soil when treated with RBI Grade-81. The soaked CBR value and free swell index of untreated soil and soil treated with 2%, 4% & 6% RBI Grade-81 at 3 days, 7 days and 14 days curing period were determined. The author has taken two soil sample A & B of expansive soils for testing. The results show that the CBR value of untreated samples A &

B were 2% & 2.19% which increased to 9.56% & 10%, 16% & 15% and 20% & 18% after 3days, 7days and 14days curing period at 2% RBI Grade-81. At 4% RBI Grade-81, the CBR values were 9.93% & 10.4%, 22% & 22% and 34.9% & 30% after 3days, 7days and 14days curing period. At 6% RBI Grade- 81 the CBR values were 10.8% & 11.5%, 27% & 26% and 53.6% & 40% after 3days, 7days and 14days curing period. Free Swell Index values decreased significantly with curing period as well as with the addition of RBI Grade-81. They also carried out a study on strength properties of problematic soils with stabilizer RBI Grade – 81 on the same soil samples A1 and A2 and with same Soil and RBI proportions. The authors have tested the soil samples for atterbergs limit, compaction and UCS and Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy of untreated and treated the soil with 6% RBI Grade-81 at 7 days curing period was conducted. The UCS value of version soil samples A1 and A2 were found to be 138 kPa and 122 kPa which were increased to 209 kPa and 130 kPa after 3 days curing and 217 kPa and 148 kPa after 7 days curing with 2% RBI Grade-81. The UCS value was increased to 742 kPa and 514 kPa after 3 days of curing and 794 kPa and 541 kPa after 7 days of curing with 6% RBI Grade-81. After the test investigation, they were concluded that the UCS value was improved appreciably with the addition of RBI Grade-81 under the curing period of 3 days and 7 days with the increase in the percentage of RBI the rate of increase of UCS also increased. The UCS value of sample A1 and A2 increased by 425% and 430% respectively after 7 days of curing period with 6% RBI stabilizer.

Objectives

The objectives of the research are outlined below:

1. To study the change in Geotechnical properties of black cotton soil by stabilizing it with RBI Grade-81.

CONCLUSION

- The strength has been compared on the basis of CBR for virgin and RBI grade-81 reinforced soil under un-soaked and soaked conditions.

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